

Skills 4 eosc

- Skills for the European
- Open Science
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THE BUILDING BLOCKS OF A Data Steward Training Curriculum

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The curriculum is aimed at instructors who can use the material to develop training for their local context. The curriculum has **8 sections** and is further sub-divided into modules.

**WHAT
CAN I
EXPECT
TO FIND IN
EACH
MODULE?**

LEARNING OBJECTIVE

LEARNING ACTIVITIES

INSTRUCTOR NOTES

RESOURCES

INTERESTED?

**SCAN OUR QR CODE
& SEE FOR YOURSELF!**

Skills4eosc

The **Skills4EOSC** project has developed a harmonised, pan-European, entry-level Data Steward training curriculum.

**SCAN ME
& DISCOVER
MORE**

TRAINING SKILLS

- Lesson development
- Facilitation and engagement

RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

- Introduction to Research Data Management
- Data documentation and storage
- Data organisation and file formats

RESEARCH SOFTWARE MANAGEMENT

- What is Research Software?
- Software Management Plans

POLICY AND GOVERNANCE

- Translating institutional policy
- Publication and reuse of research outputs

USAGE RIGHTS AND LICENSES

- Getting familiar with EU Copyright Law
- Publication and reuse of research outputs

ETHICS

- Understanding research integrity
- Ethical guidelines and legislations relevant for research

- Targeted at **entry level Data Stewards**
- Based on the **Minimum Viable Skillset** essential skills and competencies for data stewards
- Designed using the **Fair by Design Methodology**

- Developed in **consultation with Data Stewards across Europe**
- Curriculum is **open and reusable** via Github

- We **reuse existing materials** and curate what is out there
- Curriculum is **modular** so you can pick and choose

- Curriculum follows a **Train-the-Trainer Mode**
- Content is designed to be taken by instructors who can **make it their own**

Skills4eosc

PERSONAL DATA AND GDPR

TRANSVERSAL / SOFT SKILLS

- Advocacy – building soft skills for impact
- Mediation and community

Skills 4 eosc

www.skills4eosc.eu

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